

Management of electric vehicles to provide energy flexibility under uncertainty

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Abstract In recent years, the adoption of Electric Vehicles (EVs) has increased driven by governments initiatives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. This increased adoption, while environmentally beneficial, has also led to a rise in electricity consumption. This paper analyses the advantages of bidirectional vehicle-to-grid (V2G) chargers for Charging Station Operators (CSOs): Electric Vehicles energy flexibility could be a valuable resource during grid congestion episodes. We analyze this flexibility proposing a two-stage stochastic programming model under uncertainty, regarding the presence of EVs at charging station. We utilize a mixed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network to generate scenarios for each charger, then, blend and reduce them into the most representatives. The results demonstrate that electric vehicles can provide demand flexibility, resulting in potential cost reductions of up to 70%, contributing to prevent power grid congestion during periods of low generation or high demand.

1 Introduction

1.1. Motivation and Background

Recently, the regulatory landscape regarding European mobility has evolved. While the European Union initially solidified the ban on new CO₂-emitting cars by 2035, late 2025 brought significant policy adjustments, with the European Commission proposing to revise the 100% reduction target to 90%, effectively allowing a small share of internal combustion engines to remain alongside the transition to zero-emission vehicle. Despite these regulatory fluctuations, the EU market has seen sustained growth in EV adoption, though the explosive rates of previous years have stabilized. By November 2025, Electric Vehicles (EVs) captured a 16.9% market share of new registrations in the EU—a notable increase from the ~13.6% baseline observed in 2024 [1].

Transitioning to electrical mobility, continues to introduce critical uncertainty into electricity demand. In 2026, grid congestion and connection delays have moved from theoretical risks to tangible bottlenecks for charging infrastructure deployment [2]. The energy requirements of EVs must increasingly be met by renewable energy to comply with the revised "Fit for 55" objectives, further amplifying grid volatility. The combination of variable renewable generation and unpredictable EV charging patterns is now a primary driver of local grid stress, leading to more frequent curtailments and the urgent need for grid reinforcement or flexibility solutions [3].

However, the optimal management of EV charging offers a proven opportunity to provide energy flexibility to the distribution grid. By 2026, Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology has transitioned from pilot projects to early commercial reality [4], charger management can adapt the changing needs of EVs to grid requirements. The potential energy flexibility offered by V2G chargers significantly exceeds that of unidirectional smart charging: (1) V2G can absorb excess renewable generation to stabilize the grid, (2) inject power back during peak demand to mitigate congestion, (3) reduce the need for costly grid upgrades, and (4) generate revenue for Charging Station Operators (CSOs) or EV owners through emerging flexibility markets. Despite these commercial advancements, precise forecasting of charger usage remains critical to ensure that the flexibility offered does not compromise the primary mobility needs of the user.

1.2. General Overview

The authors of [5] introduce a multi-step EV charging occupancy prediction method using a mixed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network. They compared the predictions generated by their tool against other well-known machine learning algorithms, such as AdaBoost, logistic

regression, support vector machine and random forest. The results showed that the LSTM neuronal network obtained the most accurate predictions. However, to the best of our knowledge, recent literature lacks applications of LSTM neuronal networks to scenario generation for stochastic programming. The existing literature focuses on other approaches for generating representative scenarios, such as forward tree construction -based on discrete variables- and dynamic tree generation -based on the Nested Distance-, as is studied in [6].

Another study [7] has revealed a critical insight: more than 59% of EV electricity demand can be deferred by up to 8 hours from the time of connection, suggesting the potential to derive added value from optimizing such charging sessions for flexibility offers. In alignment with this, study [8] conducts an analysis and optimization of potential flexibility from a vehicle fleet perspective, employing clustering techniques to group EV users based on their vehicle usage patterns. Concurrently, authors in [9] explore the flexibility potential that Germany and California (USA) can offer, considering the optimal management of EV batteries. Their findings underscore the importance of integrating electric vehicles as valuable flexibility providers through optimization techniques. However, to avoid expensive voltage regulation mechanisms is critical a good coordination among car parking flexibility provider, Distributor System Operator (DSO) and Transportation System Operator (TSO) as the overview of [10] reflects.

Regarding modeling techniques, a variety of approaches have been used in the literature: [11] introduces a Mixed Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) model with probabilistic constraints; [12] introduces an innovative approach using a rolling horizon framework -a closed loop optimization with self-feeding information-; and [13] employs a stochastic modeling within a three-level game theory framework to approximate uncertainty associated with some parameters. In this work, we consider a two-stage stochastic programming model, fed by representative scenarios.

1.3. Contributions and Organization

This paper extends the previous research on energy flexibility from the electricity demand side to the prosumer side through V2G technology. It adapts, expands, and innovates the optimal energy management of EV fleets, with the following key contributions:

- A stochastic model that incorporates uncertainties about EV presence at chargers.
- Generation of flexibility bids that adjust the changing needs of EVs to match the requirements of the distribution grid, resulting in economic benefits.
- The usage of mixed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network to generate representative scenarios to feed a stochastic model.

The paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we elaborate the forecasting module, scenario generation, and reduction methodology. Section 3 presents the stochastic programming model formulation for optimal flexibility bid generation. In Section 4, we examine a specific case and present our numerical results. Finally, Section 5 and Section 6 convey the conclusions and future work of this paper respectively.

2 Occupancy forecasting methodology

2.1. Deep-Learning forecasting module

We designed the Deep-learning forecasting module to acquire predictions of EVs arrival and departure time. To achieve this, we employed a mixed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network based on the model presented in [5]. The LSTM is fed by historical charging occupancy state data, time of the day, day of the week and an average charging occupancy rate.

2.2. Scenario generation and representative reduction

One of our main contributions is the novel application of LSTM networks for EVs presence scenario generation to feed stochastic model, not previously found in literature to the best of our knowledge. To create these scenarios, we trained the LSTM by solving a non-linear problem. A step-by-step explanation of the scenario generation and representative reduction is described below.

Step 1: For charger n , train M mixed LSTM neural networks with different initial values for their weights and obtain the corresponding M predictions. Then generate the $L = M^N$ scenarios permuting them.

Step 2: Compute the Kantorovich distance between all pairs of the L scenarios generated in Step 1.

$$K_{(i,j)} = \sqrt{(l_i - l_j)^2} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}, i < j \quad (1)$$

Step 3: Generate the hierarchical clustering of the scenarios considering Kantorovich distances and, generate $\mathcal{S} = |\mathcal{S}|$ clusters of scenarios with similar patterns.

Fig. 1 Graphically representation of the scenario generation and representative reduction.

Step 4: For each cluster, choose the most representative scenario, s , and include it in the set of representative

scenarios, i.e., $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S} \cup \{s\}$. Consider N_s^C as the cluster represented by s .

Step 5: Choose the most representative scenario, s . Then define the probability of each representative scenario s as the number of scenarios included inside its cluster, N_s^C , divided by the total number of scenarios, N^T .

$$\pi_s = \frac{N_s^C}{N^T} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (2)$$

Table 1 Variables & Parameters

Symbol	Description	
Sets		
\mathcal{T}	Set of time steps, $\{0, 1, \dots, t_{T-1}\}$	
T	Total number of time steps, $T = \mathcal{T} $	
\mathcal{N}	Set of chargers, $\{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\}$	
N	Total number of chargers, $N = \mathcal{N} $	
\mathcal{L}	Set of scenarios, $\{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_L\}$	
L	Total number of scenarios, $L = \mathcal{L} $	
\mathcal{S}	Set of reduced scenarios, $\{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_S\}$	
S	Total number of reduced scenarios, $S = \mathcal{S} $	
Deterministic parameters		
Δt	Increment of time between time steps	0.25 h
$SO C_n^{out}$	Disconnection SoC required, [%]	100 %
$SO C_n^{ini}$	Initial SoC, [%]	50 %
$\overline{SO C_n}$	Maximum SoC allowed, [%]	100 %
$\underline{SO C_n}$	Minimum SoC required, [%]	15 %
EB	Battery capacity [kWh]	40 kWh
Pen^α	Penalty cost [€/kWh]	[14]
\overline{p}_n^{BC}	Battery maximum charge power, [kW]	10 kW
\overline{p}_n^{BD}	Battery maximum discharge power, [kW]	10 kW
γ_n^{BC}	Battery charging efficiency, [%]	98 %
γ_n^{BD}	Battery discharging efficiency, [%]	98 %
$SO C_n^{fir}$	Actual SoC, $t = 0$, [%]	50 %
p^A	Grid power, kW	76 kW
λ_t^b	Energy buying price, [€/kWh]	[14]
λ_t^s	Energy selling price, [€/kWh]	[14]
λ_t^{fU}	Flexibility increase price, [€/kWh]	[14]
λ_t^{fD}	Flexibility decrease price, [€/kWh]	[14]
Stochastic parameters		
$X_{n,t,s}^{occup}$	Binary indicator of EV presence, {0,1}	
$X_{n,t,s}^{new}$	Binary indicator of EV arrival, {0,1}	
$X_{n,t,s}^{out}$	Binary indicator of EV departure, {0,1}	
π_s	Probability of each scenario, [0,1]	
First stage variables		
$p_{1,t}^{FU}$	Increment consumption bid when buying, [kW]	
$p_{2,t}^{FU}$	Increment consumption bid when injecting, [kW]	
$p_{1,t}^{FD}$	Decrement consumption bid when buying, [kW]	
$p_{2,t}^{FD}$	Decrement consumption bid when injecting, [kW]	
x_t^f	Binary indicator of flexibility bids, {0,1}	
Second stage variables		
$p_{n,t,s}^{BD}$	Discharging power of charger, [kW]	
$p_{n,t,s}^{DOWN}$	Discharging flexibility power, [kW]	
$p_{n,t,s}^{BC}$	Charging power of charger, [kW]	
$p_{n,t,s}^{UP}$	Charging flexibility power, [kW]	
$p_{t,s}^{Ib}$	Power from grid, [kW]	
$p_{t,s}^{Is}$	Power to grid, [kW]	
$SO C_{n,t,s}$	SoC of EV at charger, [0,1]	
$x_{n,t,s}^c$	Binary status charging for charger, {0,1}	

$x_{n,t,s}^d$	Binary status discharging for charger, {0,1}
$x_{t,s}^b$	Binary status consumption from grid, {0,1}
$x_{t,s}^s$	Binary status injection to grid, {0,1}
$\alpha_{n,t,s}$	SoC of EV not satisfied on departure, [0,1]

3 Stochastic model

We introduce a stochastic mixed integer linear model, build upon its deterministic formulation. The primary objective of the model is to determine the optimal charging profile for a charging station, aligned with the forecasted occupancy of V2G chargers. Our optimal management model maximizes the charging station profit through two strategies: offering potential flexibility services and leveraging energy arbitrage opportunities. Table 1. describes the set of parameters and variables included in the stochastic optimization model. If is unspecified, the index domains are: $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$, $\forall s \in \mathcal{S}$, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$.

3.1. Objective function

The goal is to maximize the function (7) to manage the profits obtained due to the flexibility bids.

On one hand, the first two terms, B^{Flex_UP} and B^{Flex_DOWN} , represent the first stage incomes. The first reflects the incomes obtained due to flexibility bids to increase consumption power. Besides, the second reflects the incomes for flexibility bids to decrease consumption power.

Fig. 2 Graphical representation of the variables used in the objective function.

On the other hand, the last two terms, C^{Energy} and C^{Pen} , represent the second stage profits and costs, respectively. The C^{Energy} term reflect the cost to balance the system for buying/injecting energy with their corresponding price, and the C^{Pen} term has been used to represent the penalization for not reaching the final desired cost.

The objective function is defined as follows:

$$B^{Flex_UP} = \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (p_{1,t}^{FU} + p_{2,t}^{FU}) \cdot \lambda_t^{FU} \quad (3)$$

$$B^{Flex_DOWN} = \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (p_{1,t}^{FD} + p_{2,t}^{FD}) \cdot \lambda_t^{FD} \quad (4)$$

$$C^{Energy} = \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \pi_s \cdot (-\lambda_t^b \cdot p_{t,s}^{Ib} + \lambda_t^s \cdot p_{t,s}^{Is}) \quad (5)$$

$$C^{Pen} = \Delta t \cdot Pen^\alpha \cdot \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_{n,t,s} \quad (6)$$

$$\max B^{Flex_UP} + B^{Flex_DOWN} + C^{Energy} - C^{Pen} \quad (7)$$

3.2. Interconnection and balance constraints

Interconnection and balance constraints used follows the power constraints used in [15]. They are used to set up the contracted power limits and establish an energy balance between consumption/charging power and the injection/discharging power limits.

3.3. Flexibility bid constraints

The following set of constraints ensures the feasibility of flexibility bids.

Equations (8) - (11) define the upper bounds for flexibility bids $p_{1,t}^{FU}$ and $p_{2,t}^{FD}$ according to the interconnection flow direction, consumption or injection energy, respectively.

$$P_{t,s}^{Ib} + p_{1,t}^{FU} \leq P^A \cdot x_{t,s}^b \quad (8)$$

$$P_{t,s}^{Is} + p_{2,t}^{FD} \leq P^A \cdot x_{t,s}^s \quad (9)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,s}^{Ib} - p_{1,t}^{FD} \quad (10)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,s}^{Is} - p_{2,t}^{FU} \quad (11)$$

Equation (12) ensures that the flexibility bids remain below the maximum admissible power capacity.

$$p_{1,t}^{FU} + p_{2,t}^{FU} + p_{1,t}^{FD} + p_{2,t}^{FD} \leq x_t^f \cdot P^A \quad (12)$$

Constraint (13) ensures that the increase of consumption bid is limited by the difference between the weighted charging power and weighted maximum charging power. Weighted measurements help the model generate more reliable offers. Equation (14) ensures that the batteries are able to store the increment of consumption due to flexibility provision.

$$p_{1,t}^{FU} + p_{2,t}^{FU} \leq \frac{\sum_{n,s} \overline{P_n^{BC}} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup}}{|S|} - \frac{\sum_{n,s} (p_{n,t,s}^{BC} - p_{n,t,s}^{BD})}{|S|} \quad (13)$$

$$p_{1,t}^{FU} + p_{2,t}^{FU} \leq \frac{\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}, s \in \mathcal{S}} (\overline{SOC_n} - soc_{n,t,s}) EB}{\Delta t} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup} \quad (14)$$

Following previous constraints, (15) and (16) serve to regulate down flexibility offers by establishing a bound using the weighted maximum discharge power and the weighted discharge power. It is imperative to ensure the feasibility of flexibility down bids regarding EV battery State of Charge (SoCs).

$$p_{1,t}^{FD} + p_{2,t}^{FD} \leq \frac{\sum_{n,s} \overline{P_n^{BD}} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup}}{|S|} + \frac{\sum_{n,s} (p_{n,t,s}^{BC} - p_{n,t,s}^{BD})}{|S|} \quad (15)$$

$$p_{1,t}^{FD} + p_{2,t}^{FD} \leq \frac{\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}, s \in \mathcal{S}} (soc_{n,t,s} - \overline{SOC_n}) EB}{\Delta t} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup} \quad (16)$$

Finally, flexibility offers related to increasing either charging or discharging power are defined. Equations (17) and (18) introduce the new variables in order to incorporate the set of scenarios in flexibility.

$$p_{1,t}^{FU} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} p_{n,t,s}^{UP} \quad (17)$$

$$p_{2,t}^{FD} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} p_{n,t,s}^{DOWN} \quad (18)$$

3.4. Chargers constraints

For all representative scenarios $s \in \mathcal{S}$, the maximum flexibility power that every charger can provide is constrained by the power exchange between the charger and the EV, as well as the maximum charger power capacity.

$$p_{n,t,s}^{BC} + p_{n,t,s}^{UP} \leq \overline{P_n^{BC}} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup} \cdot x_{n,t,s}^c \quad (19)$$

$$p_{n,t,s}^{BD} \leq \overline{P_n^{BD}} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup} \cdot (1 - x_{n,t,s}^c) \quad (20)$$

$$p_{n,t,s}^{BD} + p_{n,t,s}^{DOWN} \leq \overline{P_n^{BD}} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup} \cdot x_{n,t,s}^d \quad (21)$$

$$p_{n,t,s}^{BC} \leq \overline{P_n^{BC}} \cdot X_{n,t,s}^{ocup} \cdot (1 - x_{n,t,s}^d) \quad (22)$$

If a charger is actively charging an EV ($x_{n,t,s}^c = 1$), then it follows that both discharging power and flexibility down must be set to zero ($p_{n,t,s}^{BD} = 0$ and $p_{n,t,s}^{DOWN} = 0$). Besides, if the charger is receiving energy from an EV ($x_{n,t,s}^d = 1$), the inverse holds true, resulting in, $p_{n,t,s}^{BC} = 0$ and $p_{n,t,s}^{UP} = 0$.

3.5. State of charge constraints

Every EV must fulfill the State of Charge (SoC) constraints for every time step $t \in \mathcal{T}$. These constraints follow ones presented in [15] and sets up SoC balance and maximum and minimum SoC bounds.

4 Results

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed two-stage stochastic model, we conducted a case study based on a residential in a university campus location [16]. The charging station considered has three V2G charging points. We examined the model performance using a set of ten representative scenarios.

We implemented the optimization problem using Python and ‘‘Pyomo’’ package and Gurobi solver. We ran it on an Intel Core i5-1235U 1.30 GHz and 16 GB of RAM. We utilized Python and R to generate mixed LSTM Neural Networks, scenarios and perform their reduction.

4.1. Deep-Learning forecasting

To evaluate the LSTM Neural Network’s mixed performance, we present the ten representative scenarios and real presence data for charger 1 in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Presence of the EV for representative scenarios and reality.

The accuracy of the presence of the EV is 70,18% for day ahead predictions. We calculated other statistical metrics such as specificity (71,11%) and sensitivity (62,46%). These values point out that Long Short Term Memory Neural Network correctly predict the EV presence for the day ahead. The differences between the real presence and predicted scenarios are subtle, meaning that reduced scenarios are representative of reality.

4.2. Stochastic optimization

Based on the results showed in Fig. 4 (a), the model demonstrates robust performance, yielding meaningful flexibility offers. Specifically, downward flexibility offers (i.e., $p_{1,t}^{FD}$ and $p_{2,t}^{FD}$) validate the model's bid modeling, aligning with interconnection status. Conversely, the absence of flexibility in $p_{2,t}^{FU}$ is attributed to the model's lack of scheduled energy injection into the main grid, thereby hindering the generation of $p_{2,t}^{FU}$ bids.

Fig. 4 (b) illustrates that the most flexible periods occur between 12:00-15:00h, coinciding with the transition from morning arrivals to afternoon departures. These hours overlap with high renewable generation periods, making it an optimal time for offering flexibility. Additionally, another period for reducing power consumption falls between 9:00 and 11:00 hours.

In Fig. 4 (c) it is evident that chargers operate at different power rates. Notably, S6 and S8 reveal instances where chargers discharge energy to assist in charging other EVs, avoiding the purchase of energy from the distribution network during peak prices periods. In the case of scenarios S2, S3, S9 and S10, charging processes occur when no cars are connected (specifically, during the period 00:00-1:30h), indicating incorrect predictions of EV presence.

These discrepancies in EV presence within the representative scenarios ($s \in \mathcal{S}$) can be attributed to LSTM variability. As illustrated in Fig. 3, scenarios S2, S3, S9 and S10 made erroneous predictions of vehicle presence at the beginning of the day. However, it is important to emphasize that these predictions effectively account for variable uncertainty and maintain a high level of overall accuracy.

Regarding costs results, negative values in Table 2. means that recharging EVs does not yield any profit for the Charging Station Operator (CSO). However, the flexibility profit reduces the charging cost by up to 70% respect the cost incurred without any energy management of chargers.

Fig. 4 Output results: (a) Flexibility bids, (b) Estimated interconnection power and Up/Down, (c) Evolution of the SoC for EVs on charger 1. Shaded zones represent the real presence of EVs.

Table 2 Optimization results

Indicator	Value	Indicator	Value
Objective function (\mathbf{z})	-6,78 €	Energy charged	160,03 kWh
Flexibility profit	23,30 €	Net energy charged price	0,043 €/kWh
Charging cost	-30,08 €	Execution time (min:sec)	11:45

4.3. Value of the Stochastic Solution & Expected Value of Perfect Information

To evaluate the true quality of the stochastic model, the study relies on two key performance metrics. The first, the Value of the Stochastic Solution (VSS), highlights why a simpler, deterministic approach is inadequate for this problem. Because a deterministic model fails to account for the inherent uncertainty of EV behavior, it proves to be completely infeasible; any flexibility offers it generated would ultimately fail to be delivered in the real world.

The second metric, the Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI), reveals how much financial value is lost by not being able to perfectly predict the future. Remarkably, the cost of this real-world uncertainty is a mere **0,08€** per day.

5 Conclusions

We found that the flexibility approach in EV charging process reduces the charging cost for the Charging Station Operator. This paper introduces a novel application of a mixed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Network to model the uncertainty of the EV presence in charging stations. Specifically, we employed this approach to generate predictive scenarios. The advantage of this scenario generation method, as compared to classic literature proposes, was that the stochastic component was better approached. The stochastic model implemented mathematical equations to establish the relation between the charging EV through Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) chargers and the flexibility bid generation. The developed procedure presented was tested using real data from [16].

In a residential case study, we performed an analysis of numerical results and discussed performance indicators. The hierarchical cluster method, employed to reduce the number of scenarios, captured the variability of the user's behavior. The Value of the Stochastic Solution (VSS) evinces that deal with variability is essential. The combination of artificial intelligence and stochastic programming exhibited high performance under uncertainty parameters. The Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI) highlights that the optimal decisions obtained closely approach the best possible outcomes in the absence of complete future knowledge.

Finally, the results demonstrate that the integration of V2G chargers and flexibility mechanisms result in a cost reduction of up to 70% in the final charging cost for EVs. In addition, besides a reduction of the charging costs, the optimal flexibility periods overlap with the peak of renewable energy generation, facilitating the integration of zero-emission generation resources.

6 Future Work & Acknowledgments

This work overlooks analysis of the battery's degradation that will be crucial to prolongate its expected lifetime. Including regulation constraints of secondary and tertiary energy markets will improve flexibility capabilities. Finally, local markets will rise as an immediate local balancing solution, the EVs integration in them will be crucial.

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